

Number of rice hills with RSNV symptoms in a sample area of 160 hills at one upland site, 56 d after emergence, Côte d'Ivoire.

Cultivar	Weed-free	Weeds present
WAB56-50 ^a	10	10
WAB99-1.1 ^a	6	36
ITA257 ^a	8	20
AUS257 ^a	7	27
Digba Youba ^b	13	22
YS236 ^b	8	9
WAB04325 ^c	0	0
ACC102257 ^c	0	0
WAB02097 ^c	0	0

^aImproved *Oryza sativa*. ^bTraditional *O. sativa*. ^c*O. glaberrima*.

the presence of RSNV in Colombia averaged 20%, with some areas incurring losses above 50%.

In an experiment in Jan 1995, the reaction of rice cultivars to RSNV was compared in plots that were either hand-weeded once or maintained weed-free. This experiment revealed differences in RSNV incidence between cultivars at different weed control levels, especially between *Oryza sativa*

cultivars that were affected to a great extent in plots with weeds (see table). The increased disease incidence in plots with weeds suggested that the disease may be encouraged by the presence of alternative hosts or that the rice plants when stressed due to competition with weeds, become more susceptible. The *O. glaberrima* cultivars in the experiment, however, were unaffected. The presence of RSNV in rice grown in Côte d'Ivoire in 1997 at the same experimental site which was affected in 1995 was positively confirmed by serological tests at CIAT, Colombia.

The high and increasing levels of crop loss caused by RSNV in Colombia necessitate studies on its distribution, mode of transmission, and control measures. Host resistance to RSNV clearly exists within *O. glaberrima*, and this could be exploited through inter-specific hybridization with *O. sativa* to produce resistant cultivars. Nowadays in West Africa, RSNV incidence is at an

extremely low level, which may be a function of the extensive nature of the upland rice production systems in the region and of the low level of mechanization. At sites in Sierra Leone and Côte d'Ivoire, where the disease has become a local problem, rice production was mechanized and relatively intensive. With the current intensification of rice-based farming systems in West Africa, the disease threatens to become increasingly more prevalent.

References

- Fauquet C, Thouvenel J-C. 1983. Association d'un nouveau virus en bâtonnet avec la maladie de la nécrose à rayures du riz, en Côte d'Ivoire. C.R. Acad. Sc. Paris 296: 575-580.
- Louvel D, Bidaux J-M. 1977. Observation de nouveaux symptômes pathologiques sur des variétés précoces de riz en Côte d'Ivoire. Agron. Trop. 32(3): 257-261. ■

Integrated pest management — diseases

Seed-borne fungi associated with rice seed lots in Pakistan

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A total of 97 seed samples collected from five locations (Lahore, Sahiwal, D.I. Khan, Hyderabad, Sukkur) were

tested from 1994 to 1996 at the Central Seed Health Laboratory of the FSCRD in Islamabad. The standard blotter method as described by the International Seed Testing Association was used. Four hundred seeds were plated at the rate of 25 seeds plate⁻¹. Seeds were incubated at 20 ± 2 °C for 7 d, and fungi were identified under a stereomicroscope.

Fifteen seed-borne fungi were detected from these seed lots (table). Of these, *Bipolaris oryzae*, *Pyricularia oryzae*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, and *Microdochium oryzae* have been reported to cause field diseases in Pakistan. The incidence of seed-borne fungi varied from one locality to another. *Cercospora oryzae*, *M. oryzae*,

Fungi detected in rice seed lots in Pakistan from 1993 to 1996.

Locality	1993-94			1994-95			1995-96		
	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range
Lahore	20	<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	0.0 - 3.2	5	<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 2.0	8	<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 3.5
		<i>Cercospora oryzae</i>	0.0 - 3.2		-	0.0		<i>C. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5
		<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	0.5 - 1.8		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	1.0 - 6.5
		<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	0.0 - 0.2		-	0.0		<i>F. graminearum</i>	0.0 - 0.5
		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	2.0 - 2.2		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	2.0 - 5.0		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.5 - 1.5
		<i>F. solani</i>	0.0 - 1.2		-	0.0		-	-
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 5.5		<i>F. semitectum</i>	1.0 - 5.5
		<i>Microdochium oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		-	0.0		<i>M. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5
		<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.5		-	0.0
		<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.8		<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5		<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5

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Table continued.

Locality	1993-94			1994-95			1995-96				
	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range	Samples tested (no.)	Fungi	% range		
Sahiwal	6	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	0.5	5	–	0.0	7	–	0.0		
		<i>Rhizoctonia oryzae</i>	0.0 - 5.8		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 1.0		–	0.0		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.5		
		<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	5.8 - 14.8			<i>T. padwickii</i>		3.8 - 13.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 5.7
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 2.5			<i>B. oryzae</i>		0.0 - 2.0		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0
		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 2.0			<i>C. lunata</i>		0.0 - 1.5		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 4.0
D.I. Khan	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 3.0		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.5		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 1.5		
		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 9.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.0 - 6.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	0.5 - 3.0		
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.5		
		<i>C. lunata</i>	1.5 - 14.5		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.5 - 5.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 4.0		
Hyderabad	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5	5	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.5 - 2.0	4	<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.5		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.5 - 2.0		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.0		
		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 0.5		
		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 27.0		<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 21.0		
		<i>F. equiseti</i>	0.0 - 0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 1.0		<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.0 - 2.5		
		<i>F. solani</i>	0.0 - 0.5		<i>F. solani</i>	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 1.0		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.5 - 1.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.5		–	0.0		–	0.0		
		<i>T. padwickii</i>	6.5 - 11.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	2.0 - 5.0		<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.0 - 4.0		
		Sukkur	5		<i>B. oryzae</i>	0.0 - 4.5		(–)	14	<i>B. oryzae</i>	1.0 - 19.5
<i>C. lunata</i>	0.0 - 0.5					<i>C. lunata</i>	0.5 - 3.5				
<i>F. equiseti</i>	0.0 - 1.0					–	0.0				
<i>F. moniliforme</i>	3.0 - 6.0					<i>F. moniliforme</i>	0.5 - 1.5				
<i>F. semitectum</i>	2.5 - 3.0					<i>F. semitectum</i>	0.0 - 2.5				
<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0					<i>N. oryzae</i>	0.5 - 1.0				
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5					<i>Phoma</i> sp.	0.5				
<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 1.0					<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	0.0 - 0.5				
<i>T. padwickii</i>	3.5 - 12.5					<i>T. padwickii</i>	1.5 - 10.0				
Total	41				19		37				

and *P. oryzae* prevailed in the Lahore area only. *Fusarium equiseti* was recorded only on seed from Hyderabad and Sukkur. Fewer seed-borne fungi were observed in seed samples from D.I. Khan. The involvement of *C. oryzae*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Phoma* sp.,

Rhizoctonia oryzae, and *Stemphylium* sp. in actual disease development has not yet been demonstrated.

Seed health testing is important to control crop diseases. The use of chemical seed treatment to improve seed quality and planting value has already

been reported. Considering the prevalence and incidence of fungal pathogens in rice seed lots, Pakistan's seed health certification program should include fungicide treatment of prebasic seeds to control field diseases. ■

Integrated pest management — other pests

Pratylenchus zeae in upland rice as influenced by ratio of intercropped maize

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In West Africa, maize is commonly relayed or intercropped with upland rice in traditional low-input systems. The density of maize as an intercrop may vary depending on many factors, including individual farmer preferences and country or region. Some nematodes that parasitize rice are common to maize, notably *Pratylenchus*

zeae, which is a pest of both crops. This study was done to examine the influence of maize - rice intercropping on the population density of *P. zeae* in rice.

Nematode densities were recorded in a trial at WARDA, established to monitor the influence of crop ratios on the incidence of stem borer pests on upland rice. The migratory endoparasite *P. zeae* and the ectoparasite *Helicotylenchus dihystrera* were present in